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APOLIPOPROTEIN E3 AND NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL OUTCOME POST TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY: AN INITIAL REPORT

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PURPOSE :

To determine whether apolipoprotein E3 (APOE-3) genotype influences neuropsychological outcome in patients with mild and moderate traumatic brain injury (TBI).

METHODS :

The preliminary data comprised 9 mild and moderate patients (one 18-year old female and 8 males, 30.50±6.33 years) diagnosed with TBI based on the Glasgow Coma Scale at the time of admission and resuscitation. Blood samples (2cc) were analyzed for the APOE gene utilizing the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) method. Executive function, verbal learning and memory, verbal fluency, and abstract reasoning were assessed twice at approximately 6 weeks and 6 months post injury. Data were analyzed using a 1-way ANOVA with repeated measures. Distributional characteristics were assessed by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the coefficients for skewness and kurtosis. For normally distributed data, a Bonferroni-corrected alpha was used to determine the differences between the psychological measures.

RESULTS :

Executive function improved from pre- to posttest (36.67±13.30 vs. 42.67±13.77, p=0.030, eta²=0.464) but this was no longer significant after the Bonferroni correction. There were no differences over time in verbal learning and memory (38.56±11.43 vs. 39.78±11.09, p=0.363, eta²=0.104), verbal fluency (19.00±9.86 vs. 20.44±7.56, p=0.457, eta²=0.071), and abstract reasoning (27.67±7.04 vs. 25.67±6.80, p=0.279, eta²=0.144).

CONCLUSIONS :

It is encouraging that the executive functioning score improved over time, which would have been statistically significant with a larger sample size although the effect size is small. The initial results seem to agree with the current findings, i.e., there might be no clear APOE genotype influence on the recovery curves of patients with mild and moderate TBI.